

Transition metal complexes of heterocyclic ligands. Part- IV. Complexes of 6-aryl-3-cyano-4-trifluoromethylpyridine-2(1H)-thione with palladium- and platinum(II)

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Manuscript received 13 March 2000, accepted 20 May 2000

The complexes of bivalent Pd and Pt with 6-aryl-3-cyano-4-trifluoromethylpyridine-2(1H)-thione have been synthesized. IR and NMR investigations show that the thiones are bonded to the metal ion through the sulfur atom. The thiones and their complexes possess antimicrobial activities.

The coordination chemistry of heterocyclic thiones has received great attention in recent years¹. A common feature of all these ligands is thione-thiol tautomerism. In the solid and neutral solution, the thione form

is the dominant tautomer with the thione sulphur atom the favoured donor site.

In a previous paper we had reported complexes of 6-aryl-3-cyano-4-trifluoromethylpyridine-2(1H)-thione with some metal(II) acetates². This presentation discusses the

preparation and characterization of six complexes of 6-aryl-3-cyano-4-trifluoromethylpyridine-2(1H)-thione (where aryl is C₆H₅³, C₁₀H₇⁴ and C₄H₃O⁴) with Pd^{II} and Pt^{II}.

LH : R = C₆H₅
L'H : R = C₁₀H₇
L''H : R = C₄H₃O

Results and Discussion

Chemical (C, H, N, S) analysis confirms one type of stoichiometry : [M Ligand₂ Cl₂], where M = Pd^{II} or Pt^{II} and Ligand = LH, L'H or L''H. The complexes are colored yel-

Table 1. Major IR band (cm⁻¹) assignments of ligands and complexes

LH	Pd(LH) ₂ Cl ₂	Pt(LH) ₂ Cl ₂	L'H	Pd(L'H) ₂ Cl ₂	Pt(L'H) ₂ Cl ₂	L''H	Pd(L''H) ₂ Cl ₂	Pt(L''H) ₂ Cl ₂	Assignment
3430	3435	3440	3440	3440	3445	3435	3430	3437	NH
1450	1450	1455	1463	1458	1460	1460	1468	1465	Thioamide I ν _{C-N} + δ _{C-H}
1240	1242	1247	1275	1268	1273	1230	1235	1228	Thioamide II ν _{C-N} + δ _{C-H} + ν _{C=S}
1080	1098	1078	1100	1110	1105	1080	1068	1100	Thioamide III ν _{C-N} + ν _{C=S}
760	780	778	770	775	780	750	765	755	Thioamide IV
735	760	762	740	750	765	730	740	735	ν ₃ (C=S) + ν _{as} (C=S)
	730	735		730	735		728	720	
650	665	645	676	660	667	670	660	675	δ _{C-S}
				635	650				
520	495	510	530	528	520	515	510	505	π _{C-S}
				535	530		525	515	

low and red, air-stable, with generally low solubility in organic solvents. Molar conductivities in nitromethane ($10^{-3} M$) show the complexes to be non-conducting (λ_M range $5.9\text{--}21.3 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$).

IR spectra of the complexes and the thiones were analysed⁵ and the results are presented in Table 1. Changes to the infrared spectra of the ligands upon coordination are restricted, essentially, to the thione region ($800\text{--}500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The thioamide IV band is particularly affected with the bands in the free ligands ($760, 735; 770, 740; 750, 703 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) replaced with sharp but split bands in the complexes. Modest shifts ($\pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and band splitting also characterise $\delta(\text{C-S})$ and $\pi(\text{C-S})$. These observations are indicative of thione sulfur donation to the metal in the prepared complexes.

Literature⁶ presents both ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra in the detection of coordination activity, but the former is rarely successful owing to the difficulty of evaluating the contribution of the thioamide group anisotropy to the chemical shift. The application of ^{13}C NMR spectra in the detection of coordination activity is more encouraging with the carbon atoms of the thione groups moved high field when the sulfur is coordinated. Taking into account these findings, ^{13}C NMR spectra of thiones and the complexes with Pd^{II} were analysed. But, in our case, the signals due to the carbon atom of the thione group in the coordinated ligands were observed at lower fields ($\delta_{\text{C=S}}$ 168.2; 153.3; 160.4 ppm) than those of the free ligands ($\delta_{\text{C=S}}$ 156.2; 139.7; 146.5 ppm). We explain this change as follows: CF_3 and CN are groups intensely attracting electrons and they reduce the order of the chemical bond in the thione (C=S) group and, by complexation, the order of this chemical bond C=S increases.

The electronic spectra of the complexes exhibit three bands between 16000 and 27000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $^1A_{2g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g} (\nu_1)$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g} (\nu_2)$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_g (\nu_3)$ transitions, respectively. These results suggest a square-planar configuration for all the complexes.

The thiones and their complexes were tested for antibacterial activity by using the dilution technique⁷ at concentrations $300, 200, 100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The results reveal that the antibacterial activity increases with increase in concentration of the compounds. The data of maximum percentage inhibition of bacterial growth at $300 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration of thiones and their complexes are as follows: *E. coli*, LH 75.09, $[\text{Pd}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

85.75, $[\text{Pt}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 89.10, L'H 78.04, $[\text{Pd}(\text{L}'\text{H})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 87.20, $[\text{Pt}(\text{L}'\text{H})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 92.25; L''H 81.27, $[\text{Pd}(\text{L}''\text{H})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 85.35, $[\text{Pt}(\text{L}''\text{H})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 95.70; *S. aureus*, LH 69.27, $[\text{Pd}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 73.35, $[\text{Pt}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 77.40; L'H 72.75, $[\text{Pd}(\text{L}'\text{H})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 75.02, $[\text{Pt}(\text{L}'\text{H})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 79.15; L''H 75.25, $[\text{Pd}(\text{L}''\text{H})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 78.02, $[\text{Pt}(\text{L}''\text{H})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ 83.70. The values reveal that the metal complexes are more active than the free thiones; the thiones and the six complexes are more active towards *E. coli* than *S. aureus* and the complexes with Pt^{II} are more active than that with Pd^{II} .

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-1600 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on an Unicam UV2-300 spectrophotometer. The molar conductivities were determined by using OK-102 Radelkis conductivity meter. The magnetic susceptibility measurement was made on a Faraday balance at room temperature. ^{13}C NMR spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on a Varian Gemini 300 BB instrument-

General procedure: The complexes were prepared by mixing an ethanolic solution of the metal dichloride with 6-aryl-3-cyano-4-trifluoromethylpyridine-2(1H)-thione in hot stirred ethanol in a 1 : 2 molar ratio. Because of the poor solubility of the thione, it was generally necessary to use a large volume of solvent and heating and stirring until the reaction was complete. The resultant solution was refluxed at 110° for 3 h, when the corresponding metal complex precipitated. It was filtered, washed several times with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

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